

Socio-economic Development Trends of Third World Countries: Success Stories and Lessons from Qatar

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ABSTRACT: The circumstances and contexts that set Qatar on a road of prosperity are gaining momentum every new day. From a small British colony country as late as 1970, Qatar has undergone evolution beginning with settling on its current name after numerous suggestions for the Arab state. Thus, the study interest was to answer two research questions; what is the basis of the success stories of Qatar and lessons for other third world countries? And Is Qatar headed to another level of categorization to leverage into the status of first world countries? The study is mainly guided by structural functionalism theory. The study entailed a systematic literature review approach through which various current literature were analyzed. The progress is largely attributed to the effective strategies entailing financial investment, cultural branding, and policy re-engineering. The political stature and efficient constitution controlled by effective leadership are contributions to milestones observed in the country.

KEYWORDS: Development Trends, Socio-Economic, Developing Countries, Qatar

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Brief historical perspectives of Qatar

Referred to as the State of Qatar, this Western Asian country was a British Colony that received independence in 1971, the same year it became a United Nations member. According to the World Factbook, Qatar is a cape country bordering Saudi Arabia and the Persian Gulf in the Arabian Peninsula. This means that Qatar is almost all-surrounded by the Mediterranean Sea and the only land border of Qatar is where it borders Saudi Arabia south way. The State of Qatar occupies 4,473 square miles (making it the eighth smallest state in Asia) with a population of 2,795,484 as estimated by its Ministry of Development, Planning and Statistics (2020). Even though the official language of Qatar is Arabic, English is also commonly used for partial communication in the country. Qatar hosts several ethnic communities, with the majority being the Arabs (40%), followed by South Asians (36%), Pakistani and Indians (18% each), Iranian (10%) and other groups of ethnic communities (14%). Qatar ascribes to Islam as its official religion.

Early historians, sociologists and archeologists have worked hard to document the birth of the Qatar State. Before the end of the first century AD, a legend Roman wrote concerning the 'Catharrei' as original dwellers of the peninsula. The Qatar National Library documents that the first ever recorded diagram of the peninsula called 'Catara' was done by Ptolemy around the second century AD. The name Qatar has metamorphosed through several variants including 'Catharrei', 'Catara', 'Katara', 'Katr', 'Kattar' and 'Guttur' until the current alternative of Qatar was settled as the state name. Etymologically, the Arabic noun Qatar has ten diverse meanings among them are land, territory, reign, and diameter.

After a war in 1867, the British replaced Bahrain's monarch, Muhammad ibn Thani al-Thani, with Muhammad ibn Thani al-Thani. As a result, the Al-Thani family has an unbroken lineage that continues to this day. In 1893, the Emir fruitfully and valiantly safeguarded Qatar against the Bahrainis and then the Ottoman Turks. In 1916, nevertheless, he made the decision to make Qatar a British protectorate.

The discovery of oil riches in the 1940s marked the start of Qatar's transition to affluence. The discovery was accompanied by deliberate plans to explore it, putting the country on a steady upward trajectory of development. In the 1940s, substantial oil deposits were discovered, which was prudently and carefully managed, and resulted in a significant change for the country. This was done to help the state's long-term development. The phenomenon resulted in the country gaining extraordinary wealth. Oil currently accounts for over 85% of the state's export revenue. So, what was the outcome? It created Qatar to be one of the world's greatest per capita incomes. Qatar was supposed to join the United Arab Emirates in the early 1970s, along with its neighboring countries. However, it turned down this offer, along with Bahrain, and declared an independent state instead (Maunder, 2021). After Crown Prince Hamad bin Khalifa al-Thani took over leadership of Qatar from 1995, he implemented a series of socio-economic reforms including increased freedom for Qataris, protection of human rights principles, and democratic elections in 1999 that permitted women to vote.

Socio-economic Development Trends of Third World Countries: Success Stories and Lessons from Qatar

Qatar's key characteristics include water shortages, climate change, soil deterioration, desertification of farms, and a loss in cultivatable land per capita. Because of the arid and semi-arid climate, it was difficult to grow food locally. Apparently, Abusin, Lari, Salma and Noor (2020) posit that food waste is one of the most serious concerns towards food security, putting weight on natural resources and limiting Qatar's ability to continue producing renewable resources. Before the blockade in 2017, 90 percent of Qatar's food was imported from neighboring countries. This pushed Qatar into the midst of a major transitioning from food insecurity towards self-sufficiency which was a difficult task.

After several restructuring and focusing on food production through scientific and technological methods, Qatar achieved near-full sufficiency in perishable goods in a very short time and produced an abundance amount of food. This highlighted the significance of sustainable manufacturing and consumption in avoiding environmental disasters like food waste, which has a direct influence on the long-term viability of arable land and groundwater. A panel of academicians, administrators, civil society, and charities met to discuss food waste sustainability and proposed policies and strategies to reduce food waste. This focused on use of compost manure for agricultural use to achieve food self-sufficiency. Managers and policymakers aided in making the best environmental decisions possible by these measures for the country.

This developmental blueprint was made factual by enthusiasm and pragmatic leadership of the country. Her Highness Sheikha Moza binti Nasir, mother of current Emir of Qatar Sheik Tamin has also made a significant contribution to Qatar's growth. This was throughout the period of her spouse Sheikh Hamad bin Al-Thani and her son Tamim where she played the role in laying down the foundation of modern Qatar. This points back to the popular saying.... *behind every successful man there is a woman*. Further, she is the co-founder and chairperson of the Al-Qatar Foundation. The Foundation is known for offering effective and friendly socio-economic services to humanity both nationally and internationally.

1.2 The Qatar Constitution and Social Development

The Qatar constitution makes several lessons relating to human rights. The constitution outcomes and advantages are pointed through various concepts that encompass political stability, international relations, human rights, and general socio-economic development. For instance, the UN (n.d.) highlights areas lessons including Qatar's strategic development policies which are guided by the rule of law. On the other hand, the rule has been signified through cultural transition. Moreover, the importance of the link between maintaining peace, development and security has been emphasized in relation to the constitution. These signify the importance of justice and safety in stability of a country. This is clear and dominant in the post-2015 progress agenda of Qatar.

In other dimensions, the considerations for the working of the constitution have been aligned to today's challenges rather than past failures and hindrances. The constitution is drawn from the UN's rule of law together with its indicators for justice and criminal prevention. These were highlighted in the 13th United Nations Congress in April 2015 which was held in Qatar. The constitution broadened the scope for economy where everyone has opportunity to invest and grow economically. It has also resulted to greater jobs creations, more opportunities for the job seekers as well as end to human trafficking and related activities. The constitution spells out the repercussions for social justice offenders which has been under implementation.

1.3 Research Questions

The study delved into exploring the state of development of Qatar and its environment that has brought about consistency in growth and gaining global recognition. Based on the background, Qatar has some basis of socio-economic development specifically the growth of its social institutions that has maintained its upward trends. While it is categorized as a third world country, its development structures and strategies can be stories and lessons for other countries. Thus, the study purposed to answer two research questions; what is the basis of the success stories of Qatar and lessons for other third world countries? and Is Qatar headed to another level of categorization to leverage into the status of devolved world countries? The analysis is based on sociological functionalist perspective which entail harmony, stability and peace among people while being a pivotal accelerator of steady development of countries.

2.0 MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study entailed a systematic literature review approach through which various current literature were analyzed. The method entailed a list of publications from journals as well as media publications. This was informed by the state of unfolding incidences and activities surrounding the involvement of Qatar in humanitarian services and developmental strategies which are ongoing as at time of the writing and release of this article. The scope consisted of articles and literature published and posted from 2015 to 2021. The study employed thematic analysis of the literature with presentations aligned to various identified themes including political hierarchy and international relations of Qatar, success stories and then drawing up to conclusions. The ethical concerns were observed through filtering the validity and reliability of the literature. This was achieved through comparisons with other existing sources including different media houses as well as blogposts.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Political Hierarchy and International Relations of Qatar

Qatar gained importance and even notoriety in the Middle East, as well as global arena, since the 1980s. The change was due to the direct result of an effective and efficient directional paradigm shift towards healthy development agenda. The blueprint agenda was engineered by the wise leadership of the state. However, the state's policies have detractors and especially from other Arab countries claiming that it supports Islamic groups, political parties, revolutions and democracy abroad. Such claims were vehemently denied by Qatar and termed as due to hallucinating envies and fear factor towards demands for democratic change by citizens of those countries.

According to Peterson (2013), Qatar's sudden prominence is the product of three overlapping endurance and influence strategies: cultural branding, economic investment, and strategy projection. Because of Qatar's tiny size and great wealth, these techniques have been desired, though not necessary. Qatar's actions, however, are not without controversy, particularly allegations that it supports Islamist groups and related activities.

The country's constitution was certified by a public referendum on April 29, 2003; the Emir endorsed it on June 8, 2004, and it went into force on June 9, 2005. The constitution was initially introduced in 2005, offering residents freedom of expression and religion. Qatar is governed by an emirate system, and the Emir Sheikh Tamim bin Hamad Al Thani has been the country's Head of State since 2013. Whereas after his father, Sheikh Hamad Al Thani abdicated the throne, Emir Sheikh Tamim took over the leadership of the state. He is also the Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces as well as the Minister of Defense. There are no elections for the emirate because it is a hereditary position. Sheikh Abdulla bin Hamad Al-Thani is the heir apparent. Prime Minister Khalid bin Khallifa Al-Thani oversees the government, while the Deputy Prime Minister is Sheikh Mohammed bin Abdulaziz Abdurahiman bin Jassim Al-Thani, who is also Qatar's foreign affairs minister.

In addition, the Emir appoints a cabinet/council of ministers, which includes the Legislative arm of the state. The Advisory Council can develop and adopt laws, but the Emir has the final word after extensive deliberation. The Council is made up of 45 members, 30 of whom are directly elected by general secret ballot and 15 of whom are chosen by the Emir. A Judicial arm is also fully in place. The Administrative Court, the Constitutional Court, and the Courts of First Instance, Appeal, and Cassation were all established in 2007. On the suggestion of the Supreme Judicial Council, all judges are selected by Amiri degree (established in 1999) who will be in office for a term of three years. The legal system is founded on Islamic and civil law systems, as well as a discretionary legal system based on culturally accepted values and principles. Islamic law dominates family, personal status and commercial law while the penal code is also sourced from Islamic criminal law.

In May 2011, Qatar held statewide elections for a 29-member Central Municipal Council (CMC), which has limited consultative rights and is tasked with improving municipal service delivery. (The CMC held its first election in March 1999). The terms are four years long, where both male and female Qataris aged 18 and above have the right to vote and run for office.

In the international arena, the Saudi-led bloc requested Qatar shut down Al Jazeera, the global news network it promotes, as one of its requirements for restoring diplomatic relations and lifting an embargo after the two countries broke ties in early June 2017. Qatar rejected the proposal, as well as the rest of the blockades demands. The media behemoth, which has given Qatar enormous clout in the Middle East and beyond, assists the small Gulf emirate in defying the GCC's larger members' foreign policy and forging its way. As a result, Qatar has refused to shut down what it considers to be an exceptional source of soft power (Laub, 2017) and source of enlightenment to the Gulf communities. Since its inception, Aljazeera has gained a wide international and regional reputation and credibility while attracting millions of viewers.

Al Jazeera has been insulated from the regular market pressures that cable television faces because of funding from Qatar's royal family. As an alternative to the region's tightly regulated state media, Al Jazeera's reportage on common concerns and protest movements has outraged powerful regimes. Al Jazeera is accused of promoting terrorism by Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Egypt, and Bahrain (Sakka & Sadik, 2021). In turn, the network accuses them of seeking to "suppress the region's freedom of expression."

3.1.1 Qatar Support to Palestinian and the oppressed

According to Gulf-Times news media house (2018), Amir Shiekh Tamim pledged to support elevation of the Palestinians in Gaza. The Palestinians who were seen as oppressed and denied their rightful possession of their land were thus given support through Qatar where the speaker of the advisory board, Ahmed bin Abdullah gave a speech quoting the determination of the Amir. This was also thought through as dedicated brotherhood among Arabs which pointed out the oppressions against the Palestine people by Israel. As a result, he continued to condemn events such as the designation of Jerusalem as the Israeli entity's eternal capital and the transfer of embassies to it with the objective of removing the issue of Jerusalem from any negotiations, as well as the unfair siege on the Gaza Strip.

Such tactics by Israel are also intended to sabotage the refugee crisis and Palestinian refugees' right to return home. Amir Sheikh Tamim also noted that the adoption of the "nation-state law" by the Israeli parliament, perpetuates discrimination and repulsive apartheid, as well as undermining any lingering aspirations for peace and a two-state solution. According to the speaker of the Advisory Council, this is also an attempt to impose forced solutions that deny Palestinians the right to an independent state and the

Socio-economic Development Trends of Third World Countries: Success Stories and Lessons from Qatar

right to return to their occupied land. Until then, and justice accorded, the conflict between Israel and Palestine will not come to an end.

Based on the need for legitimacy for human rights, HE al-Mahmoud, the deputy prime minister, stated that the meeting was taking place at a time when the number of Palestinian martyrs and wounded continues to rise. Consequently, recurring peaceful demonstration informs the occupier of the Palestinians' steadfastness in their claim to their legitimate right to return and reclaim their lands.

3.1.2 Afghanistan Taliban Takeover – Qatar Intervention

According to Economic news (2021), Qatar has an outstanding role in the process of the US trying to evacuate people from Afghanistan since the Taliban takeover following the US troops exit. Qatar is seen as a helper in safeguarding the predicaments of Afghanistan through its laid bonds with both Washington and the Taliban which have taken over Afghanistan. Through a virtual meeting held by Antony Blinken – the US secretary of states, Qatar was noted as a key player in the efforts to settle the US decision to leave Afghanistan. Likewise, other countries and organs that sort help from Qatar include NATO, France, Canada, the United Kingdom, Italy, the European Union, among others. President Joe Biden personally expressed his gratitude to Qatar's 41-year-old Emir Tamim bin Hamad Al-Thani over the phone, according to the White House. The president noted that the US-led airlift would not have been possible without Qatar's assistance in facilitating the daily transfer of thousands of people. It's the kind of positive publicity that millions of dollars spent on lobbying and public relations by other Gulf Arab states could hardly guarantee such popular achievement.

The Taliban are said to have asked Qatar to provide civilian technical assistance and renovation at Kabul's international airport once the US military withdrawal ended. The Qatar government, indeed, acted swiftly in restoration of the effective services in the airport within a short period. Meanwhile, UN agencies across the world were seeking Qatar's help and collaboration in delivering aid to Afghanistan. Qatar's participation came as a shock. The country, which shares a land border with Saudi Arabia and a huge offshore gas field in the Persian Gulf with Iran, was supposed to be a transit point for tens of thousands of people fleeing Afghanistan over the course of a few months.

Following the Taliban's startlingly swift takeover of Kabul on August 15, 2021, the United States and European countries turned to Qatar for help in evacuating tens of thousands of their citizens in a chaotic and hasty airlift. A fact revealing to the country's dependability, neutrality, and trustworthiness. In the end, Qatar has earned praise from Washington and the rest of the world for transporting over 40% of all evacuees out of the country. Qatar was also the shield for international news organizations to evacuate their workers.

Since August 14, 2021, the US has evacuated 113,500 civilians from Afghanistan. Qatar said that 43,000 migrants had crossed its borders. Qatar's participation in the evacuations reflects both its prominence as the largest US military base in the Middle East and its decision years ago to shelter the Taliban's political leadership in exile, giving it tremendous power with the militant group. The United States and the Taliban also met in Qatar for peace talks. To date, Qatar plays a pivotal role in mediating the negotiation between the Taliban, the US and Europe. Lolwa al-Khater, Qatar's assistant foreign minister, acknowledged Qatar's political advances in recent weeks but dismissed any claim that Qatar's actions were solely strategic.

She told the Associated Press;

If anyone assumes that it's only about political gains, believe me, there are ways to do PR that are way easier than risking our people there on the ground, way easier than us having sleepless nights literally for the past two weeks, way less complicated than spending our time looking after every kid and every pregnant woman
[30/08/2021]

Qatar carried out some of the most sensitive rescue missions in Afghanistan with only a few hundred soldiers and military jets. A girls' boarding school, an all-female robotics team, and international media journalists, among others, were evacuated from Afghanistan. Qatar's envoy to Afghanistan led bus convoys past a maze of Taliban checkpoints in Kabul, as well as many Western military checkpoints at the airport, where vast crowds had gathered, desperate to flee. After receiving requests from foreign organizations and vetting their names, Qatar facilitated access to the airport for 3,000 people and airlifted as many as 1,500, according to al-Khater.

Al-Khater adds that Qatar is in a unique position because of its capacity to communicate with a variety of stakeholders on the ground and its willingness to escort people into Taliban-controlled Kabul. "What a lot of people don't realize is that this journey isn't about making a phone call to the Taliban," she explained. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) points out that Qatar is the host and Mediator between ongoing various negotiations between Afghanistan-Taliban delegation one side and, separately each, of those from US, Canada, UK, and EU countries on different issues concerning the future of Afghanistan (Barakat, Milton and Elkahlout, 2019).

Al-Khater continued, "There are checkpoints on the US, British, NATO, and Turkish sides... and we have to juggle all of these variables and factors." All those who stay in Afghanistan have been promised amnesty by the Taliban. Despite this, many of those desperate to flee, including civil society activists, former Western army personnel, and women fearful of losing hard-won rights, say they do not trust the Taliban.

Socio-economic Development Trends of Third World Countries: Success Stories and Lessons from Qatar

Other armed organizations are also posing a rising threat. An Islamic State suicide bomber killed more than 180 people near Kabul airport in August 2021. Miscalculation and disarray hampered the US-led evacuation operation from Kabul, which spilled over to Qatar's al-Udeid base for help. During the climax of the evacuation efforts on August 20, the hangars at al-Udeid were so crowded that the US suspended flights from Kabul for many hours. Several thousand evacuees were accepted by neighboring nations like Bahrain and the United Arab Emirates to relieve pressure on the American base.

Afghan families evacuated by the US waited in poorly ventilated, steamy hangars in the middle of the desert with inadequate conditioning for hours at al-Udeid. Hundreds of evacuees were seen in one such hangar, with only one lavatory and people sleeping on the ground, according to a video provided by The Washington Post. To help cover the gaps, Qatar built an emergency field hospital, more shelters, and portable washrooms. In addition to what the US military was distributing, the Qatari military distributed 50,000 meals per day, with local charities distributing ample necessities.

Qatar Airways also dispatched ten planes to transfer evacuees from Doha to other nations. As late as 30th August, around 20,000 evacuees remained in Qatar, with some expected to leave in the following weeks and others in the following months as they waited to be resettled elsewhere. Since their arrival in Qatar, seven Afghan women delivered babies. Qatar is absorbing just a very limited number of evacuees, among them a group of female students who will be awarded scholarships to complete their education in Doha. Qatar also accommodated some evacuees in furnished apartments meant for the FIFA World Cup, which will be held in Doha next year (2022).

3.1.3 Bilateral relations between Kenya and Qatar

The Embassy of Kenya in Qatar, like the Kenyan community in Qatar, is doing a fantastic job of bringing the two countries closer together by participating in numerous social, cultural, and sporting activities. Paddy C Ahenda, a former member of Kenya's Parliament, was appointed Kenya's Ambassador to Qatar in March 2019, to take bilateral relations to new heights of cooperation (The Peninsula Daily newspaper, 04 Mar 2019). After his appointment, ambassador Ahenda said that he wanted to serve not just his country, but also the entire continent of Africa, by infusing new life into the current strong Kenya-Qatar relations. His comparison of Africa's location and role in international corporation pointed to Nairobi as a hub for UN and other countries across the globe for development. Nairobi being a home to Un-Habitat and UNEP showed that it has the potential for the world in hosting not only international corporations but also contribute to investments negotiated through meetings in the city.

In relation to Qatar, the ambassador called out the country to focus on investing in Nairobi especially in real estate as the demand and the potential has been growing annually. The housing demand has shown potential for Nairobi housing investment to make yields within short periods. This is also informed by the growing population in the city with expected doubling in the next three decades. The existing bilateral agreements between Kenya and Qatar makes it more hopeful that the coexistence and collaborations between the two countries will live on. Based on the anticipated hosting of FIFA world cup in 2022, Kenya and Qatar share a special interest in sports and culture through which the bond is strengthened.

Moreover, through the conflicts and attacks of the Somali-based militia groups and terrorists, Al-Shabab, Qatar has played a critical role in restoring peace between the two countries (The Doha Globe, May 7, 2021). After the existing feud between Kenya and Somali over allegation of Kenya meddling in Somali's politics, the intervention of Qatar led to settling of the differences and re-establishment of diplomatic relations. Through the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Qatar, Doha promised to use its rich bilateral relations across the globe in harmonizing the relations between Kenya and Somali (Bukhari, 2019). In other dimensions, Qatar has reached out to help Kenya in agriculture sector which is the economic backbone of the country.

The Kenyan ambassador to Qatar noted that through agro-sector, Qatar showed potential in foreign investment that would expedite the growth through the agriculture sector. The ambassador fronted that Qatar could invest in Kenya in organic vegetable and fruit production owing to availability of rich farming land, water for irrigation as well as affordable farm labor. Similarly, the Qatar ambassador to Kenya, Jabr Bin Ali Al Dosari noted that his country had interest in using technology in agriculture to enhance yields in Kenya. He, further, emphasized for the existence of other future cooperative and developmental engagements between the two countries to enhance joint interests and prosperity. He also affirms the relationship between Kenya and Qatar being at its zenith (capital Business, 2021). He said this during a courtesy call to the late billionaire businessman Dr. Chris Kirubi in his Nairobi home.

3.2 Success Stories from Qatar

3.2.1 Recent blockages and sanctions by its neighbors

Despite its economic success at home and abroad, according to Maunder (2021), Qatar had one of its most serious crises. Saudi Arabia, Bahrain, Egypt, and the United Arab Emirates (UAE) established an embargo on Qatar in June 2017. The boycott was based on allegations that the nation supports terrorist groups. The boycott was quite significant to Qatar's economy as about 60% of its imports came from countries that sanctioned it.

Qatar suffered the blockade through the effect on business lines, and more painfully, the closure of its fifth Airways' route. Making it worse, the deportation of Qatari people from the neighboring countries was a human cost situation. Qatar bravely resisted to comply with its neighbors' demands for more than three and a half years since the blockade began. One of the demands of the

Socio-economic Development Trends of Third World Countries: Success Stories and Lessons from Qatar

neighboring countries was to close Al Jazeera media. However, the country consistently kept good ties with other countries including Turkey, the US and Iran as it explored more bilateral trade potentials.

The lifting of the sanctions in January 2021 was the welcome of the long-awaited response to calls to end the feud. The calls started as early as 2016 (Jeddah, 2017). France had persistently called for lifting of the sanctions on Qatar, especially to settle the challenges shown through the gaps between Qatar and its neighbors. Reported through the foreign minister, Jean-Yves Le, when he met the Qatar prime minister, HE Sheikh Mohamed Bin Abdulrahman al-Thani, France called for urgent sanction lift. Jean-Yves Le further paid a visit to Gulf mediator Kuwait, US and UAE, which finally came to succeed. In addition, the campaign for lifting of the sanctions was through interventions of other countries like Germany since 2016.

After the lifting of the sanction, Qatar opened the Hamad Port, which is now the largest in the Middle East. The port is thought to play a role in creating access and movement of goods and services. Despite Qatar airways losing all destinations within the blockading countries, it defied all odds to maintain its income and stability. Doha majorly became active routes to Iran where supply of more foodstuff and medicine were significant in imports. Moreover, the stronger connection to Turkey created greater military pact where technology and innovations in the sector was enhanced.

According to Siddell, Iqbal, Dackiw, Safar-Aly and Slim (2021), the lifting of the sanctions against Qatar came in after the signing of the "Al-Ula Declaration," to end the limitations posed against Qatar. This was done on 5 January 2021 during the 41st GCC Summit at the city Al-Ula, Saudi Arabia. While the signing of the declaration has never been made public, but it ultimately ended the blockade against Qatar by Bahrain, UAE, Saudia Arabia and Egypt.

The lifting of the sanction has since created new opportunities through the reopening of the borders. This has restored the cross-border transit to and fro Qatar. The free movement of the cargo and passage planes between UAE and Qatar was accelerated through both planned and unscheduled flights cleared by the aviation authorities (Arabian Business, 2021). Abu Dhabi harbour master cleared the movement of ship vessels and boats between UAE and Qatar after the minister of Energy released a circular to end the restrictions on 8th of January 2021.

3.2.2 Self-reliance and flourishing engineered by the embargo

The sanction circumstances that had befallen Qatar put it in an innovation state which came out as an advantage. This was a real reflection of the proverb "*necessity is the mother of invention*". The country had to undergo a significant shift in policies. According to Yaakoubi (2018), Qatar went out to revitalize through a 5-year development strategy that would overcome the sanction by the other Arab countries. The National Development Strategy between 2018-2022 was aimed at rationalizing the energy sector through focusing on sufficiency in agriculture and especially fish farming. The Prime Minister plans that by next year (2022), 30% of the animal farm requirements are met with over 65% of fish needs achieved.

The food production and security statistics show that quite over 2.7 million people in Qatar rely on imported food (Statistica Research Department, 2020). This is attributed to the country's desert land where only about 6% is arable. The food security situation worsened for the country when UAE, Egypt, Saudi Arabia and Bahrain sanctioned Qatar. The boycott through banned transportation into and outside Qatar created import challenges causing import fall by over 40%. While the country suffered on the sanction, it explored more options and used its rich gas production to create more income through coalitions with other countries. Moreover, the food shortage was cushioned through extra food imports from Turkey, the US and Iran.

The strategies have put Qatar on a recovery trajectory where the quarter of 2017 saw the country invest more in animal production through technology. Apparently, experts predict that the diplomatic row is likely to endure for more years despite the lifting of the sanctions. Some of the unfolding cases that accelerate the feud include the alleged infringement on Qatar's airspace by UAE military plane. As the country strive to have resilience towards the challenges, the strategic plan focusses more on ensuring that its citizens are well protected and enjoy the social environment through sports and thus improve physical health.

Ibrahim (2020) points out that the blockade of Qatar from other Arab countries became an impetus for it to thrive in various areas to be a self-reliant country. For instance, three areas of significance included food security, trade and travel. Qatar relied on dairy product imports from Saudi Arabia for food security before the blockade, with 400 tons of milk and yoghurt arriving every day (Statistica Research department, 2020).

Qatar, on the other hand, set up several long-term projects within months of the siege. Thousands of cows were imported from Europe and the United States, and Baladna - the country's first dairy and meat farm were established. As a result, the Gulf state was able to become more self-sufficient in terms of food, and even began to export dairy products. Many local businesses collaborated with dozens of farms to supply retailers with fresh fruits and vegetables. During the coronavirus pandemic, efforts to improve Qatar's food security became increasingly important.

As a result of the embargo, large warehouses were stocked with vital staples such rice, oil, and sugar, ensuring that grocery shelves remained stocked during the peak of the pandemic weeks, even as basic supplies ran out in many countries around the world. The shift, according to Nasser Al Khalaf, CEO of the Agrico Agriculture Company, was aided by domestic technology. As late as 2017, the local production of vegetables and fruits was below 10 percent. Today (2021), the country is almost 30 percent. Since the technology and know-how is available locally, there is nothing to stop Qatar from reaching its targets.

Socio-economic Development Trends of Third World Countries: Success Stories and Lessons from Qatar

The Global Food Security Indices indicates that Qatar is rated first in the Middle East and 13th globally for food security (The Economist Group, 2021). Qatar's economy has shown robust growth despite the embargo and shocks from the 2014-16 reduction in hydrocarbon prices. The efforts for global food security are still within its priorities. For instance, the fourth international food security conference held between 7-9 October 2021 took place in Doha. Through the conference, Qatar designed agenda for the G20 countries through the 7th conference of Parliamentary Speakers in Rome, Italy where concerns such as their responsibility towards Afghanistan's food security were discussed.

Other challenges have still faced Qatar making its achievements becoming unique across the globe. One of the most challenging area was when the world hit its lowest energy costs in April 2021 (Krieg, 2021). While COVID-19 pandemic has put many countries on the verge of economic crises, Qatar has had the least impact due to its self-reliance statuses. This was well achieved through the strategies that cushion the country from dependence on foreign donations and funding.

3.2.3 Reasons for winning hosting Olympic Games / 2022 FIFA World cup

Munday (2021) reports on the global questions surrounding the world cup 2022 hosts, Qatar. Several countries around the world were debating whether Qatar is truly qualified to host the World Cup. It's a question that only came to the lips of some of Europe's most notable footballers and nations. However, in 2010, FIFA gave Qatar the right to host the 2022 World Cup, defeating out bids from the United States, South Korea, Japan, and Australia on the ballot. And despite the uproar and opposition from various quarters, mainly the European clubs of whether Qatar with no previous history in sports and football heritage can have the capacity to host such a great and important global event in 2022.

Regardless, Qatar proved to its detractors and the entire world otherwise. It has boosted the maintenance to the sustainability of sports venues and infrastructure to a world standard. It also built 8 new complex stadiums and other necessary contingency facilities demonstrating its capability to host the event to perfection. In addition, the finals were also moved to winter to combat the extreme summer heat. Therefore, whatsoever the objectives of the oppositions were, the world is finally, and fully set for the event to be held in Qatar willy-nilly.

As Qatar prepares for the FIFA World Cup in 2022, a slew of arts and culture projects have sprung in the last three years. Qatar's National Museum, a \$500 million facility that showcases national culture and history, as well as wildlife and scientific achievements, opened in 2019. Qatar has also spent billions of dollars in recent years acquiring world-renowned art to display in its cutting-edge institutions. Patriotism has grown among Qatar's almost 2.7 million people in recent years, with Qatari flags and stylized pictures of Emir Sheikh Tamim bin Hamad Al-Thani adorning towers throughout the capital.

3.2.4 Support to Nations during the Covid-19 pandemic

Countries all over the world are in a grave situation because of the Coronavirus "Covid-19" outbreak, which has expanded at an unprecedented rate across five continents, causing serious difficulties in a variety of crucial industries. Even though the State of Qatar is taking the required measures to govern its domestic health situation and protect itself from the Corona outbreak and its ramifications across numerous sectors, Qatar has not forgotten its humanitarian responsibilities to its fraternal and friendly nations and has mobilized all resources to help those in need (Bukhari, 2021). This demonstrates its exemplary support for nations during this difficult time.

Since the outbreak of "Covid-19," Qatar has supplied emergency medical assistance to over 78 nations to assist them in dealing with the situation. As a result, the pandemic's ramifications will be reduced while the virus's combat circle will be expanded globally. Various authorities in the state, such as the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Ministry of Defense, the Qatar Fund for Development, charitable organizations, and the private sector, have extended their full support to deliver this aid to the needy countries promptly and efficiently (International Cooperation Department of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, August 2020).

Despite the conditions, Qatar Airways played a critical and conspicuous part in the delivery of this help, transporting one million displaced individuals around the world and securely returning them to their homes. Qatar Airways has won appreciation from governments all around the world. Qatar continues to provide unrelenting aid to needy and distressed countries peerlessly and without border limits out of a sense of humanitarian duty and obligation.

The State of Qatar provided over \$50 million in foreign aid to combat the Corona pandemic, benefiting 32 countries on five continents. Aside from the several field clinics offered by the Ministry of Defense, the State also provided 150 million dollars in financial assistance to the Gaza Strip. The portions of that went to help the health sector cope with the impacts of the Corona crisis. Qatar also allocated 20 million dollars to the Global Alliance for Vaccines and Immunization (GAVI) out of its belief in the urgency of confirming international support and political commitment. This facilitated the speeding up of research and clinical testing, leading to the vaccine and cure medication. This in turn spread over to international organizations, humanitarian and civil society associations.

The state also announced a ten-million-dollar investment to the World Health Organization (WHO) to assist speedy access to technology for testing, treatment, and provision of a sufficient vaccination for "Covid-19". This aimed at saving lives and making it available to all world residents, leaving no one behind.

The Qatar institutions, philanthropic groups, and private sector enterprises were also quick to respond and provide needed support. This has helped lessen the hazards posed by the coronavirus outbreak around the world. Foreign aid contributed by nonprofit

Socio-economic Development Trends of Third World Countries: Success Stories and Lessons from Qatar

organizations, businesses, and the private sector in Qatar totaled around 39 million dollars, which was distributed to 66 nations throughout the world. Medical relief and financial support were offered through the organization's offices around the world. Institutions and private enterprises, such as Qatar Charity, Qatar Red Crescent Society, Al Majida Group, "Baladna Food Industries," Qatar National Bank, and Qatar Airways, Al-Qatar foundation coordinated with Qatar diplomatic offices in the host nations to carry out this noble task.

Qatar ambassadors to these nations provide the aid, according to Reliefweb (2020), highlighting the country's humanitarian role and help to friendly countries in the light of the pandemic, as it strives to support countries affected by the coronavirus' spread. Officials from these countries appreciated Qatar's involvement in preventing the spread of the coronavirus and aiding friendly countries in such a difficult time upon receiving the aid. They also expressed gratitude to the State of Qatar for providing humanitarian aid, saying that the Qatari government and people are actively involved in assisting those affected by natural disasters, with a focus on civil society's health and safety to prevent the pandemic from spreading.

The outline of the beneficiary countries included Kosovo, Somalia, Pakistan, Chad, Malaysia, Nigeria, Kyrgyzstan, Morocco, Libya, Mongolia, Malaysia (UNHCR in Kuala Lumpur), Senegal, Tajikistan, Kenya, Albania, Kingdom of Eswatini, Venezuela, Croatia, the Bahamas, Haiti, Ecuador, Paraguay, Liberia, San Marino, Mexico, Nicaragua, Montenegro, Cameroon Costa Rica., Bolivia, Cuba, Romania, Peru, Dominican, Armenia, Central Africa, and South Africa together with other countries.

Qatar Charity has been swift to respond to the coronavirus pandemic, hoping to prevent it from spreading. Through its offices in 30 countries, it has been able to provide medical, protective, and food assistance to 600,000 people, totaling over 40 million Qatari riyals. The reaction to the coronavirus by Qatar Charity is anticipated to cost 13,687,500 Qatari riyals. The campaign was carried out by Qatar Charity in conjunction with UN and international organizations like as UNICEF, UNHCR, and the International Organization for Migration. More than one million people benefited from assistance offered by Qatar Charity offices and embassies around the world, as well as international organizations.

Sectoral policy analysts including the author are of the view that if Qatar retains and maintains its current development pace, it will become a leading world powerhouse for prosperity and financial hub in the next decade. This been discussed in other literature which points out the likelihood of paradigm shift in the power rank of countries in the post-covid 19 techsavvy world (Omar and Patrick, 2020). This also calls for empirical execution and enhancement of the set development frameworks. Without exaggeration, it would be the next "Dubai" that is, it may surpass the Dubai business stature.

4.0 CONCLUSION: PROSPECTS FOR QATAR

Branding and investment have increased the visibility of the small country while also ensuring future profits. Neither, however, guarantees the country's power and influence — individually nor in combination. As a result, the government has focused on the third pillar of its overall strategy, policy projection or "soft power," in recent years (a better description than power projection, since Qatar, has very little actual power beyond its deep purse). From the beginning of his rule, policy projection appears to have been one of Sheikh Tamim's primary goals. He had a proclivity for daring, but dangerous regional policies from the beginning of his reign: Sheikh Tamim appeared to take the risky path of snubbing Saudi Arabia on several issues, culminating in Saudi Crown Prince Abdullah's boycott of a Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) summit in Doha and the cancellation of a natural gas pipeline connecting Qatar and Kuwait that would have crossed Saudi territory. Then, even though an International Court of Justice ruling in 2001 resolved a long-standing series of border concerns with neighboring Bahrain, relations between the two countries remained tense, and plans for the ambitious Bahrain-Qatar causeway were placed on hold in 2010.

Sheikh Tamim was able to take these risks because he ensured Qatar's security by expanding his partnership with the United States and providing it with facilities in Qatar, including the al-Udeid airbase, which also houses the United States Central Command forward headquarters. These facilities proved to be of great use both before and during the Iraq invasion, ensuring that the emirate garnered widespread media attention as well as the US and its allies' gratitude.

After securing the country's safety, the Sheikh embarked on an ambitious strategy to put his country on the diplomatic map by convening discussions in Doha with: a focus on a World Trade Organization ministerial meeting that provided Qatar with additional exposure as part of the ongoing Doha Round of trade talks; the U.S.-backed Middle East and North African Regional Economic Meeting, with Israeli representation; Summit of the Organisation of Islamic Conference; the United Nations Conference on Climate Change (2012); the Group of 77's Second South Summit; and its appointment to the United Nations Security Council for a two-year tenure (2005). Qatar also in her endeavor to build goodwill provided \$100 million in help to the United States in the aftermath of Hurricane Katrina in 2006, as well as a promise to spend considerably in France's impoverished suburbs in 2012.

Sheikh Tamim has been working to develop a broader, more overtly activist foreign policy in recent years, initially through conciliation and subsequently through participation in regional issues including facilitation of signing of agreement between Sudan and Eritria in Doha, Qatar. There was also the mediation of a ceasefire between the Yemen government and Houthi rebels by Qatari representatives in Yemen.

The success stories for Qatar can be attributed to stable financial resources created from rich oil reserves. The usefulness of the resources has been turned in to humanitarian concerns through professionalism and patriotism. The accommodative nature of Qatar

Socio-economic Development Trends of Third World Countries: Success Stories and Lessons from Qatar

which focusses on inclusiveness of all the nations across the globe has given them an advantage for reaching out the world at large. The investment and love for research through advanced technology has ensured greater opportunities accompanied by strategic leadership. These have been wrapped by innovative and effective policy formulation and implementation. Thus, if Qatar maintains the development pace in research and technology, and humanitarian services without boundary limits, it may be equated to the stature of the first world countries in the next few decades.

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